

Combining Confidential Computing and Unikernels for Lightweight Confidential Computing

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Abstract

While the integrity and confidentiality of data can be guaranteed by confidential virtual machines (CVMs), this is only part of the chain-of-trust when deploying sensitive workloads on untrusted infrastructure. Any vulnerability inside the CVM can potentially undermine its integrity, making verification and hardening of the (full) software stack essential parts of the security of the system. Unikernels—library operating systems that statically link to the application to produce a minimal bootable image—are effective approaches to reduce the Trusted Computing Base (TCB). We present SEV-Unikernel, the first general purpose unikernel compatible with AMD’s CVM, SEV-SNP. SEV-Unikernel is language agnostic and runs in a standard hypervisor without any external dependencies. Our prototype fully supports the native SEV attestation mechanism, enabling the measurement and attestation of the entire software stack and the proactive detection of integrity faults. We demonstrate the practicality of SEV-Unikernel on a variety of microbenchmarks and real-world workloads. Our experimental results show that SEV-Unikernel achieves a significant TCB reduction with respect to confidential Linux virtual machines. We observe almost no overhead on compute intensive workloads, but implementation weaknesses in the network stack cause a 1.3x to 12x overhead for network-intensive benchmarks.

1 Introduction

Trusted execution environments (TEEs) are a class of security features found on certain CPUs that enable running computations in isolation from their host environment. They can be used for various things, such as protecting cryptographic functions from malicious applications on the host, protecting proprietary algorithms on devices, or gen-

erally running any program on un-trusted remote hosts. They can be divided across two categories: *process*-based TEEs (enclaves) and *virtual-machine*-based TEEs (confidential VMs).

Process-based TEEs, such as Intel SGX [7], provide primitives to secure single processes, called *enclaves*. Initially present on both consumer- and data-center-grade CPUs, Intel SGX had the dual goal of helping secure computation in the cloud and enabling running security-sensitive applications, such as digital rights management (DRM) software, on client devices. An Intel SGX enclave consists of only a small amount of code, typically a single executable binary, or even a part of it. Its small size simplifies the analysis of SGX application security: excluding attacks against SGX itself, the security analysis is limited to the code running in the enclave and the inter-process communications set up by the enclave. However, its main drawback is the lack of flexibility, making it challenging to run unmodified (legacy) applications in a trusted manner.

VM-based TEEs, such as Intel TDX [26], ARM CCA [35], and AMD SEV [21, 22, 28], enable the execution of *confidential virtual machines* (CVMs) instead. This provides more flexibility when deploying confidential workloads on remote servers, since the management of a CVM is very similar to that of a classic (non-secure) VM. However, this flexibility comes at a significantly increased *trusted computing base* (TCB) that needs to be audited for security. Indeed, a security analysis now has to include everything that is running in the VM, including the firmware, the bootloader, the kernel, all the shared libraries, the kernel drivers, and the other software running in the VM besides the protected application (such as an SSH daemon, loggers, *etc.*).

While process-based and VM-based TEEs can coexist on the same CPU (*e.g.*, Intel SGX and TDX), AMD never shipped a process-based TEE, and the industry tends to switch to VM-based TEEs. Interestingly, Intel has discontinued SGX for its consumer-grade CPUs, and now focuses on providing TDX on server-grade CPUs, similar to what AMD does already on its server-grade EPYC processors with Secure Encrypted Virtualization (AMD SEV).

This calls for methods to drastically reduce the amount of code running in a CVM, enabling users to benefit from

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both the flexibility of VM-based TEEs and the lower amount of trusted code required by a process-based TEE. Existing approaches to reduce the trusted computing base rely on an intermediate bytecode language, such as WebAssembly [8], or use a minimal kernel together with shared libraries from the host to provide a Linux-compatible environment [32].

This paper presents a solution that more faithfully reproduces the properties of process-based TEEs on AMD SEV processors, while supporting the flexibility given by CVMs. SEV-Unikernel, our system, is a unikernel [36] for AMD SEV. By compiling everything (the full execution stack) into a single statically linked bootable executable, unikernels entirely eliminate the need for external dependencies at runtime. Our study of SEV-Unikernel security properties demonstrates its advantages in secure environments. SEV-Unikernel supports an attestation mechanism (§5) to allow remote users to verify the integrity of the SEV-Unikernel application running inside an SEV CVM.

We study its security properties in §6, and evaluate its performance on a variety of workloads in §7.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We propose a unikernel design which can run Linux applications on the AMD SEV platform with a reduced TCB;
- We present and implement an attestation mechanism that allows remote processes to verify the digest of a running SEV-Unikernel application;
- We evaluate the performance of our system on multiple micro-benchmarks and benchmarks representative of real-world use cases;
- We release our implementation as open-source code and will contribute our modifications to the Hermit [9] unikernel, on top of which we built our work.

2 Background

2.1 Trusted Execution Environments

TEEs allow one program to run in a trust bubble on an otherwise untrusted machine. This bubble typically takes the form of memory encryption, as well as a variety of additional hardware measures that ensure that the workload running in the TEE cannot be observed or altered by other processes running on the machine, the operating system, or even certain classes of hardware adversaries.

TEEs have seen wide deployment on end-user client devices in the form of ARM TrustZone, which is present on most smartphones and smart-devices [41], and Intel SGX [7], which was available on end-user CPUs released between 2015 and 2021, before the technology was relegated to server-grade hardware only.

In recent years, the focus of TEEs has shifted towards cloud computing, leading to the release of a new generation of VM-based TEEs, or *confidential VMs*: Intel TDX [26], AMD SEV [21], and Arm CCA [35]. These TEEs enable the execution of full virtual machines, isolated from their host environment, through full memory encryption, thereby re-

ducing the operational complexity of running confidential computing payloads.

2.2 AMD SEV

AMD SEV [21, 22, 28] is AMD’s implementation for confidential virtual machines (VMs). In this work, we always refer to SEV-SNP as the current iteration of this technology when writing AMD SEV. The memory of an AMD SEV VM is transparently encrypted by the CPU with a VM specific key generated during the start-up sequence of that VM. This guarantees that neither the host operating system, hypervisor, other VM on the host, nor even a physical adversary passively listening to the memory bus can see the content of the encrypted VM memory. To access memory-mapped input/output devices and for host communication, AMD SEV allows the guest to control the encryption of a specific memory page by setting a bit (*C-bit*) in the physical address of that page.

Because SEV-SNP encrypts the register contents to prevent attacks caused by malicious hypervisors [25], emulation of certain instructions by hypervisors is no longer directly possible, as reading the instruction inputs and writing their outputs requires access to the VM’s registers. To facilitate this, AMD introduced a shared memory page called the *guest-hypervisor communication block* (GHCB), in which the guest writes register values before passing control to the hypervisor and reads these values when the hypervisor returns. This provides a more restricted communication interface between the VM and the hypervisor, allowing the guest to perform additional security checks before using the GHCB. Figure 1 illustrates the steps performed in this process. Additionally, the GHCB can be used by the guest to communicate securely with the AMD SEV firmware, which is necessary to obtain attestation reports or keys.

2.3 AMD SEV Threat Model

As detailed in [28], AMD SEV-SNP protects the confidentiality and integrity of the virtual machine in the presence of a malicious OS or hypervisor context. In addition, thanks to the use of memory encryption, AMD SEV protects the confidentiality of the VM in the presence of a passive adversary that can read the content of the DRAM chips, for example, through a cold boot attack or by passively listening on the memory bus. The threat model of AMD SEV only trusts the AMD CPU itself and the SEV virtual machine— all other software and hardware components are considered untrusted. On the side of the VM, the threat model assumes that precautions have been taken by the OS developer to protect its interfaces and its I/O.

The threat model of AMD SEV explicitly excludes denial-of-service attacks from the host, where a malicious hypervisor refuses to return control to a confidential VM. A number of known hardware and side-channel attacks for AMD SEV are known at this time [20, 24, 44, 49] highlighting real security issues. Our work is orthogonal, and we consider these attacks outside the scope of the considered

Figure 1: Typical interrupt flow in an AMD SEV VM: The VM executes an instruction that requires hypervisor intervention (1). The CPU then gives control to the hypervisor (2), and the hypervisor resumes the VM with a #VC exception (3). The guest parses the current instruction and determines what information to write in the shared memory page (4), then returns control to the hypervisor with the vmcall instruction (5). The hypervisor uses information from the GHCB to emulate the instruction and writes the result values in the GHCB (6). It then resumes execution of the VM (7). On resume, the guest reads the response registers it expected from the GHCB (8) and resumes execution.

threat model. We make the assumption that the underlying hardware is side-channel attack-free, either due to updated firmware or new CPU hardware.

2.4 Attestation

In the context of TEEs, attestation designates the technical means by which a user (the *Verifier*) can verify that a confidential VM or process (the *Attester*) is running on a correctly configured TEE. In AMD SEV, attestation relies on the processor producing and signing an attestation report [28, 40]. This report contains information about the state of the AMD SEV firmware, including its version and enabled features, as well as a launch digest that identifies the content of the VM memory at boot. In addition, the attestation report can contain 512 bits of arbitrary data, which can be used to produce an attestation about a specific application state, such as the digest of a key exchange or a challenge provided by the user to prevent replay attacks.

The launch digest included in AMD SEV attestations is computed during the VM boot process [16]. Before starting the VM, the hypervisor inserts memory pages into the guest’s memory using an SNP-specific command, SNP_LAUNCH_UPDATE. Some of these pages include the code that the VM will jump to at boot. When such pages are inserted, AMD SEV encrypts them using a VM-specific key and computes their SHA-384 digest. When the VM is finally launched using the SNP_LAUNCH_FINISH command, AMD SEV stores the

final digest as the launch digest that will be included in all future attestations during the lifetime of this VM.

2.5 Unikernels

A unikernel [36] is a single-address space image consisting of only a single application. This is achieved by statically linking an operating-system kernel library with the user program and its dependencies into a bootable binary. This approach results in a single-address space application, making system calls for context switches superfluous. Instead, all kernel functionality is accessed via function calls. This approach reduces the system overhead and can also be beneficial for security by reducing the quantity of code that needs to be audited.

3 Related Work

Linux Kernel. Guest and host support for AMD SEV in the Linux kernel has been contributed by AMD and already enables booting Linux guests as AMD SEV VMs¹. However, even specially optimized Linux kernels include hundreds of drivers and subsystems that are not useful in an AMD SEV VM, and are typically around 60-70MB big once compiled. In addition, a Linux distribution includes a large amount of user-land software that can be exploited by an adversary to compromise a VM.

WebAssembly runtimes. Some projects, such as Enarx [8], Twine [37], or WATZ [38], provide WebAssembly runtimes that run in TEEs. WebAssembly is a bytecode format initially developed for the web platform, but which also found use outside of the browser. The WebAssembly platform does not provide an equivalent to all-important POSIX APIs, and just-in-time compilation by the WebAssembly runtime incurs a performance penalty [37]. In SEV-Unikernel, we instead rely on ahead-of-time compilation and linking to produce directly executable and bootable binaries.

Gramine-TDX. Gramine [45] is a security-focused libOS that is binary compatible with Linux. It was used in Gramine-SGX [46] to enable running unmodified applications on the Intel SGX platform. Then, Gramine-TDX [32] implemented a minimal OS kernel to enable running Gramine binaries on the Intel TDX platform and within a VM. Gramine’s approach targets binary compatibility with Linux and, to that aim, relies heavily on dynamic library loading. Gramine-TDX loads verified binaries from the host into the guest’s memory, which may cause unnecessary code to be included in the application’s memory space. Despite this, they achieve remarkably low TCB sizes, often even lower than those achieved by SEV-Unikernel. However, their work is only available for Intel TDX and therefore does not support AMD SEV.

IncognitoOS. IncognitoOS [23] is an AMD SEV compatible unikernel that implements full-system obfuscation through

¹<https://git.kernel.org/pub/scm/linux/kernel/git/torvalds/linux.git/commit/?id=408323581b722c9bd504dd296920f392049a7f52>

randomization of memory pages. This work addresses the important question of protecting CVMs against side-channel attacks. While the performance hit they achieve is impressively low considering the protection mechanisms employed, it is still high enough to warrant a simpler operating system that does not provide these generic protections. We highlight that as part of their work, authors of [23] released AMD SEV implementation patches for the Unikraft [31] project, another unikernel. However, the authors have not explored the security and performance of these patches in their work, nor have they examined the question of attestations.

Container-based approaches. TEEs can also be established in container runtimes such as docker, which utilize the host kernel and make use of confidential computing hardware. Representatives of this approach are frameworks like Confidential Containers [10] and the Oak Project [3]. Confidential Containers offer a so-called pod-centric approach in which multiple containers can operate in a single TEE and share their data securely without any additional overhead. This is a compromise between reducing the TCB (i.e. as it were in a container-centric setup) and being able to quickly and more easily share data between different containers.

In Oak Containers, applications are wrapped in Enclave Applications running in an OCI runtime which can attest themselves to other nodes with the help of hardware-bound keys. One enclave can communicate with other enclaves or to the outside via their complementary Host Application that transfers the encrypted data. Alternatively, Oak also offers the possibility to wrap the application in their own restricted microkernel which offers very limited features and has reduced performance but keeps the TCB minimal.

Both Confidential Containers and Oak Containers are similar to SEV-Unikernel in the sense that they aim to provide higher isolation between running entities than regular containers can provide. However, SEV-Unikernel reduces its overhead as a VM by being tailored to the application and offering full kernel functionalities, while these containers use the host kernel, reducing the isolation.

4 Approach

SEV-Unikernel is based on Hermit [9, 33, 34], a unikernel implemented in Rust. Hermit supports various micro-architectures (x86-64, aarch64, RISC-V), hardware devices (virtio, rtl8139, mmio/ioio serial ports, PCI/PCIe, ACPI, ...), network stacks (TCP, UDP, VSOCK), and protocols (DNS client, DHCP). It supports multi-core processing, although the network stack does not support concurrency. In addition, it supports mounting file systems shared by the host through virtiofs [11]. All the additional features of the kernel are gated by conditional compilation flags and can therefore be disabled and excluded from the kernel.

The unikernel approach produces binaries with no external dependencies, which can be optimized to include only the code required by the application. This is useful in terms of security, as theoretically only code that is directly used by the program is included in the final binary. This contrasts with the libOS approach used by Gramine [32], which relies on loading dynamic system libraries at startup. Even if most functions of these libraries are not called by the program, they still form part of its memory space and can therefore be leveraged by adversaries to exploit memory bugs in executed parts of the program, for example, through *return-oriented programming* attacks [43].

Hermit does not target binary compatibility with any other operating system; however, it aims to provide POSIX-compatible APIs for all of its features. This compatibility is implemented at two different levels:

- For Rust applications, Hermit provides a patched Rust standard library that directly calls into the kernel functions, without the need to rely on a POSIX-compatible API at all.
- For C applications, Rust applications that require a C library, and other applications written in C-compatible languages, Hermit provides a newlib [12] port which implements the C standard library. We observed experimentally in §7 that compiling C code with SEV-Unikernel produces bigger binaries than compiling Rust code.

4.1 Implementation

We developed a set of modifications to Hermit which together implement the AMD SEV extensions and allow Hermit VMs to boot in AMD SEV. SEV-Unikernel benefits from the existing implementation work of Hermit, such as its wide range of supported configurations, which can be enabled or disabled selectively depending on the program’s needs. As Hermit is an open-source project, we intend to submit SEV-Unikernel patches to Hermit authors with the goal to include them upstream.

In details, SEV-Unikernel:

- Implements the physical address modifications required by the presence of the *C-bit*, controlling encryption status of a page;
- Establishes a GHCB page per core and registers it with the host, avoiding reliance on the firmware GHCB implementation;
- Implements a handler to #VC exceptions, which securely parses and interprets the trapped instruction before returning control to the hypervisor;
- Provides some *exit shortcuts*, which allow the kernel to directly call into the hypervisor when executing operations which require hypervisor cooperation, such as writing to the console – essentially skipping steps 1-3 of Figure 1, in a mechanism similar to traditional hypercalls [18];
- Exposes the AMD SEV guest interface as a device file under `/dev/sev-guest`, to enable easy source compatibility

Figure 2: Attestation Mechanism: from boot to attestation

with Linux programs that rely on that interface for attestation or key generation [2, 29].

While implementing AMD SEV extensions for this work, we also contributed some fixes and additional features (including some missing system calls and a different memory allocator) to the base Hermit kernel, some of which have already been adopted upstream.

In total, this implementation work represents 6.8k additional lines of Rust code contributed to the Hermit kernel.

4.2 Firmware and Bootloader

While Intel TDX offers a combined firmware and bootloader solution called *td-shim* [27], there is currently no alternative for AMD SEV, and developing one is outside the scope of this research. Instead, SEV-Unikernel relies on two typical software components used when booting a virtual machine: the *firmware* and the *bootloader*.

The firmware is loaded by the hypervisor in the VM memory before boot. As explained in §2.4, this means that the launch digest included in AMD SEV attestations is roughly equivalent to the SHA-384 digest of the firmware. The bootloader is loaded by the firmware and, in turn, simply loads and boots our application.

When creating an AMD SEV VM, QEMU inserts some variables in the firmware code, to allow the VM to locate AMD SEV specific data-structures in memory. QEMU’s implementation assumes the firmware used is the Open Virtual Machine Firmware (OVMF) [42], and will therefore not be able to load a firmware that does not support firmware variables in a way compatible with OVMF. For simplicity reasons, and because we are not aware of any other compatible firmware implementation for AMD SEV, we use a slightly customized build of OVMF as firmware. Our OVMF build removes features that are not useful in a CVM, such as the interactive setup menu or the splash screen. As detailed in §5, we can further configure our OVMF build to include

secure boot keys and a digest of the kernel as additional variables, ensuring that the launch digest depends on them.

For the bootloader, we use Hermit’s own loader, a thin bootloader developed by the Hermit authors, which simply locates a Hermit application and boots it. We modify the loader to enforce Secure Boot (i.e., the loader refuses to boot unless Secure Boot is enabled on the VM) and kernel integrity verification (the loader verifies that the kernel’s digest matches a known acceptable value stored in the OVMF). We further detail these measures in §5. In addition, the loader locates the AMD SEV specific pages mentioned previously (the SEV-SNP *CC blob*) and passes its address to the kernel.

5 Attestation

Without modifications, one cannot use an AMD SEV attestation to determine precisely what programs are running in an AMD SEV VM. Indeed, as discussed in §2.4, the launch measurement included in attestations reports is a digest of the memory of the VM at launch, which in the case of QEMU VMs typically consists exclusively of the OVMF firmware. This problem is particularly important on Linux: while OVMF variables allow for verification of the Linux kernel and initial ramdisk [39], verifying the content of the mounted disk or running binaries is not straightforward.

Thankfully, the unikernel approach used in SEV-Unikernel makes the attestation problem simple in comparison: there is always a single binary loaded in the VM, and after the boot process is completed, that binary is the user program. Solving the problem is therefore a matter of providing verifiable evidence in the OVMF, and ensuring that each boot step verifies this evidence before allowing the boot to continue. Given an OVMF binary, remote users can then extract the evidence, and if the evidence matches expectations, they can compute the digest and compare it with the launch measurement observed in the attestation.

Figure 3: Attestation Mechanism: building a trusted OVMF and obtaining the expected measurement

We present the complete boot process of an attested SEV-Unikernel VM in Figure 2. As explained, each boot step needs to verify the next step before executing it. This process begins in the OVMF, where we enable the standard secure boot features and include application-specific keys. The secure boot module of OVMF compares the hash of our bootloader against its database of allowed hashes before allowing it to run, and aborts the VM if it does not pass this verification. Similarly, our bootloader then reads the hash of the expected SEV-Unikernel binary from a custom OVMF variable and compares it with the loaded kernel before allowing it to run. Once started, the SEV-Unikernel application can then use the AMD SEV guest APIs to generate an attestation, which includes the digest of the OVMF as the launch digest.

To verify the integrity of a running SEV-Unikernel binary from an AMD SEV attestation, remote users need access to the OVMF binary used in the VM. This binary is constructed by combining compiled firmware code with variables, both of which can be distributed by the party running the VM. Users verify that the base OVMF image is trustworthy by using a list of known-good images. Then, they verify that the loader hash in the OVMF variables also matches a known-good bootloader. After verifying the OVMF and loader, users can be confident that the running binary has been correctly verified by the loader, which means the digest of the running application is the one included in the OVMF variables. As part of our project, we provide a small demonstration script that obtains an attestation from an HTTP server running in AMD SEV and, given an OVMF file, verifies that the VM was correctly booted with that firmware and prints the hashes of the loader and kernel.

We depict the build process of a modified OVMF firmware, as well as the variables involved, in Figure 3. To start, the developer builds their SEV-Unikernel application and retrieves (or builds) a copy of the bootloader and an empty OVMF file. They then generate a set of cryptographic keys, as specified by secure boot standards. They first generate a Platform Key (PK), which they use to sign a Key

Enrolment Key (KEK), which they in turn use to sign a signature database containing the loader hash. To avoid any risk of leaks, they then immediately delete the private keys and only keep their associated certificates. Then, they patch the OVMF firmware and insert the PK, KEK, signature database, as well as an additional custom variable that contains the SEV-Unikernel application digest. We provide a Python script that, provided with the bootloader, empty OVMF, and a kernel hash, outputs a modified OVMF file with the correct variables set.

6 Security Analysis

The threat model of SEV-Unikernel is identical to that of AMD SEV itself [28]: we aim to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the data processed in SEV-Unikernel in the presence of a powerful adversary with complete control of the operating system, hypervisor, and the ability to access the physical hardware to perform passive attacks. The only trusted components in a SEV-Unikernel deployment are the AMD SEV secure processor and SEV-Unikernel itself.

6.1 Attack Surface

Because everything outside of a SEV-Unikernel VM is un-trusted, we must take special care to protect all the interfaces between our kernel and the outside of the VM. In particular, we cannot assume that drivers comply with the specification, and we should not assume that data structures shared with the hypervisor are safe to use.

SEV-Unikernel’s attack surface includes all the parts of the kernel where host interaction is required:

- **VC handler and GHCB.** The emulation of certain instructions, such as memory-mapped I/O, requires cooperation of the host. When such cooperation is required, the host injects an exception (`#VC`). SEV-Unikernel handles this exception by writing and reading data from a shared memory page, the GHCB, and then handing control over to the host (exiting).

Attack surface: the host may inject spurious exceptions with arbitrary data; it may respond to well-formed exits with arbitrary data to corrupt SEV-Unikernel; it may corrupt the GHCB.

Counter-measures: SEV-Unikernel always parses the instruction that caused a `#VC` exception to determine what registers to share with the hypervisor when delegating the call. Any incorrect instruction will cause the VM to abort. Only the registers that are needed to emulate the instruction (typically, the instruction result) are read after resuming from the exit, meaning the hypervisor has no capacity to rewrite arbitrary registers, including the instruction pointer.

- **I/O registers.** SEV-Unikernel reads from and writes to I/O ports using the specialized `inb/outb` instructions to implement reads from and writes to the serial console.

Attack surface: the host may inject spurious interrupts to disrupt the execution flow; it may insert arbitrary bytes on the virtualized I/O port.

Counter-measures: As the `inb` instruction reads only one byte at a time, it does not have the potential to directly corrupt memory. Our implementation reads inputs to a fixed-sized buffer, and stops reading when the buffer is full. Out-of-bound accesses to this buffer are additionally prevented by checks inserted by the Rust compiler. Furthermore, we do not use the `inb/outb` instructions, but instead use the GHCB directly, avoiding a `#VC` trap when calling these instructions.

- **VirtIO devices.** SEV-Unikernel relies on VirtIO for persistent file-system support (through `virtiofs` [11]) and network emulation. At boot, the kernel reads ACPI registers to locate the different PCI buses and enumerates devices on them. It then tries to initialize network cards and file systems among those devices.

Attack surface: the host may insert arbitrary devices in the PCI configuration; it may provide a bogus PCI bus base address to cause the guest to rewrite its own memory; it can arbitrarily modify the data in shared VirtIO buffer; it can provide malicious VirtIO devices that do not comply with the specification to try to cause bugs in the guest.

Counter-measures: When initializing PCI devices, SEV-Unikernel verifies that their physical address cannot overlap with the guest physical memory, to prevent the host from writing at arbitrary addresses during PCI device discovery. The VirtIO data-structures are protected in guest memory, and pages shared with the host are only accessed from protected abstractions.

- **CPUID.** SEV-Unikernel relies on the `cpuid` instruction to determine support for certain CPU features.

Attack surface: the host may provide incomplete or incorrect responses to `cpuid` requests, trying to force the guest to disable certain security features.

Counter-measures: AMD SEV allows the hypervisor to specify certain `cpuid` values when booting a VM, and these values are verified by AMD SEV hardware during the boot process. When a `cpuid` instruction is issued, SEV-Unikernel tries to respond directly by reading the value from that page. If the value is not present but is security critical, SEV-Unikernel will crash on the `cpuid` instruction instead of potentially returning wrong values. This currently only applies to the AMD SEV features vector.

6.2 Programming language choice

The choice of Rust as a programming language for SEV-Unikernel provides memory safety guarantees for most of the kernel code [30, 47]. Outside of functions and blocks of code marked with the `unsafe` keyword, the Rust compiler ensures that certain classes of bugs, such as buffer overflows or use-after-free, are not possible.

Figure 4: Illustration of the use of safe Rust and unsafe Rust in SEV-Unikernel. **Red** blocks represent un-trusted memory, which may be corrupted by a malicious host. **Orange** blocks represent unsafe Rust wrappers around reads and writes to the un-trusted memory areas. In unsafe Rust, the compiler can not guarantee the absence of memory bugs. These parts of the code, therefore, require extra care to ensure no such bug can occur. When these blocks and their assumptions are correct, the Rust compiler ensures that the **green** blocks of code (safe Rust) do not have any memory bug.

As show in Figure 4, the source code of SEV-Unikernel is composed of some blocks of unsafe code, used to interact with the hardware – where the compiler cannot provide any guarantees – which are wrapped in safe abstractions that are used in the rest of the kernel. As long as the unsafe blocks do not introduce them (for example, by using dangling pointers, or initializing arrays with incorrect lengths), the Rust compiler ensures that memory bugs are not possible in the kernel. In SEV-Unikernel, the entire interface with the hypervisor is considered unsafe, and is therefore never accessed directly by the rest of kernel code. This reduces the area that has to be especially hardened and audited for security to only the unsafe Rust portions.

7 Evaluation

We provide a quantitative analysis of SEV-Unikernel, studying its performance in a series of microbenchmarks and real-world programs. In addition, we provide a detailed analysis of the TCB size of the different benchmarks in §7.6.

We compare the performance of SEV-Unikernel both in standard and SEV VMs with Linux (both standard and SEV VMs) and Gramine [32] (standard and TDX VMs). We only consider virtualized systems, as service isolation is a primary goal in confidential computing. For a fair comparison, we compile all applications from scratch with an effort to match optimization and feature flags on all systems. Leveraging Gramine’s binary compatibility to Linux, we use the same binaries for Linux and Gramine benchmarks.

Since Gramine-TDX and SEV-Unikernel require two distinct CPU systems, we cannot compare SEV-Unikernel and Gramine-TDX directly on the same server. Instead, we run the benchmarks on two different machines and scale all results from the TDX machine, using the (non-confidential)

Linux VMs results as a reference. We compute this scaling factor separately for each reported benchmark result.

Benchmarks for AMD SEV were run on a server equipped with an AMD EPYC 9124 16-Core 3.7 GHz processor. Benchmarks for TDX were run on a server equipped with an Intel Xeon Gold 5515+ 8-core 4.1 GHz processor. Both servers are equipped with 64 GiB of memory and run Ubuntu 24.04 LTS. The AMD SEV host uses a locally compiled Linux kernel 6.11.0-rc3 with SEV-SNP host patches at commit 85ef1ac03941, while the TDX host uses a pre-compiled Linux kernel 6.8.0-1028-intel, provided by Kobuk Team.² For Linux VMs, we run an Ubuntu 24.04 cloud image³ built by Canonical on August 5th, 2025—which natively supports AMD SEV.

7.1 Boot time

So-called Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) workloads have become popular in the past years. In these trigger-based executions of user-defined functionality, fast boot times can significantly reduce the overall system load, motivating us to evaluate the time it takes to boot a VM. The start of the measurement is right before the invocation of `qemu` (or, for Gramine, before invocation of the `gramine-vm / gramine-tdx` script), and we measure until a specific log message is printed to the console. This is the TTY welcome message for Linux and the last kernel log message before control is handed over to the application for Hermit and Gramine. We note that Linux and Gramine have higher minimal memory requirements than SEV-Unikernel.

We can see in Figure 5 that under AMD SEV and TDX the boot-time of SEV-Unikernel and Gramine is directly

Figure 5: Boot time comparison. (*) Gramine results are scaled.

dependent on the memory size. For lower amounts of memory, SEV-Unikernel boots faster than plain Linux VMs and Gramine. However, in an AMD SEV setting, this advantage is lost, and SEV-Unikernel VMs with more than 8GiB of memory boot slower than Linux. Mapping memory lazily when it is used (instead of mapping it entirely during boot) may alleviate this issue and should be investigated in future work.

7.2 UnixBench

We start with the classic UnixBench benchmark suite, which we slightly modified to work around the lack of support for signals in SEV-Unikernel. In some benchmarks, a timer signal is used to guarantee a fixed runtime, which we replaced with a second thread that calls `usleep`. File-system benchmarks (`fstime`, `fsbuffer` and `fsdisk`) were run both using an in-memory file-system (`-tmp` suffix) and a `virtiofs` share on the host (no suffix). As illustrated in Figure 7, Linux performance on `virtiofs` is slower by a factor of 5 to 10, we therefore omit these results from our main graph for readability reasons.

We report the UnixBench results in Figure 6. We note that the performance of the three systems does not significantly

²<https://launchpad.net/~kobuk-team/+archive/ubuntu/tdx>

³<https://cloud-images.ubuntu.com/noble/>

Figure 6: UnixBench Results. Linux `virtiofs` results excluded for readability (see Figure 7). (*) Gramine results are scaled.

Figure 8: Lighttpd performance. (*) Gramine results are scaled.

Figure 9: Web framework performance

differ in compute-heavy benchmarks. We see an average slowdown caused by AMD SEV/Intel TDX of 9%. If we break this down, we see an average slowdown of 0.3% for compute workloads and 30% on file system accesses. which is in line with the reported values in related studies [1, 17, 48].

7.3 Web Server & Frameworks

Here, we benchmark the lighttpd web server [4] (written in C), as well as two Rust web application frameworks axum [5] and hyper [6].

Figure 7: Virtiofs accesses on Linux perform significantly worse than the other systems.

For lighttpd, we use the wrk HTTP benchmarking tool to retrieve two files of sizes 100B and 10kB hosted by a lighttpd server running in a VM. The benchmark runs for 30 seconds, keeping 100 connections open across 8 threads. The VM itself is provided with 1 CPU core and 4GiB of memory. The server configuration and the two files are mounted in the VM using virtiofs, except in the SEV and TDX Linux VMs, where these files are mounted as a FAT32 partition.

Our results (Figure 8) are comparable to those reported in [32]. Neither SEV-Unikernel nor Gramine reach the network performance of Linux in both classic and confidential settings. SEV-Unikernel performs better than Gramine for the larger page runs, but slightly worse for the 100 Byte payloads. We note that SEV-Unikernel has a rather consistent performance penalty of ~15% when running in AMD SEV, whilst Gramine-TDX does not suffer any slowdown compared to Gramine-VM for the large payloads, but only reaches half of the performance of Gramine-VM for the

Figure 10: Valkey performance. (*) Gramine results are scaled.

Figure 11: SQLite performance. (*) Gramine results are scaled.

small payloads. As shown in [19], 10kB page size are more representative to real-life content served by web-servers.

For axum and hyper, we rely on the *TechEmpower Web Framework Benchmarks* framework [13]. We use their reference axum and hyper applications, and specifically benchmark the axum-mongo, axum-pg and hyper-pg variants. We run the servers in a VM provisioned with 1 CPU core and 8 GiB of memory and additionally expose a MongoDB and PostgreSQL database on the host. The benchmarked application implement the three following tests: *JSON Serialization*, *Single Query*, and *Fortunes*. *JSON Serialization* serializes and returns a freshly-instantiated object with a single key and string value ; *Single Query* retrieves a row from the database and returns it serialized in JSON ; *Fortunes* fetches Unix fortune cookie messages from a database table and returns them in a rendered HTML template. A more precise description of these tests is available in [13].

We report the results of these benchmarks in Figure 9. Due to a limitation in Gramine-TDX, programs running in Gramine VMs can not access databases running on the host, and we therefore report no result for this platform in this benchmark. We have confirmed this is a generic issue in Gramine-TDX by trying (and failing) to run other network-client programs in Gramine-TDX.

For SEV-Unikernel, running in AMD SEV only results in an average slowdown of less than 2% (compared to 15% on Linux). However, this is likely due to the poor performance of SEV-Unikernel on these network heavy benchmarks. Indeed, the performance of SEV-Unikernel is approximately 11x worse than Linux. We investigated this performance issue and attribute it to limitations in the scheduler in Hermit, which are amplified by the nature of the axum and hyper frameworks, which rely heavily on asynchronous tasks. Asynchronous tasks implement collaborative multi-

tasking and they rely on the scheduler waking them up once processing is ready to continue, something that does not happen as fast and consistently as it should in SEV-Unikernel. We leave improving the scheduler to address these issues for future work.

7.4 Databases

We benchmark the in-memory key-value store Valkey [14], a fork of Redis, and the SQLite [15] self-contained relational database.

For Valkey, we run a Valkey server in a VM, and run the valkey-benchmark utility from the host. We configure the tool to run with 48 parallel connections, each running up to 8 operations in advance (pipelining). The Valkey VM itself is allocated a single core and 16GiB of memory. We report the results in Figure 10.

Similarly to the other benchmarks, Linux outperforms SEV-Unikernel and Gramine usually by a factor of two. Gramine performs on average 8% faster than SEV-Unikernel in plain VMs, and 16% faster when running in their respective TEE. Linux suffers an average slowdown of 23% in a confidential environment, whereas SEV-Unikernel only perceives 11%, and Gramine only takes a 5% penalty.

The SQLite benchmark, *kvtest.c*, is part of the SQLite source code, and consists in the execution of a fixed number of reads and writes in a database with 100k rows, each between 8kB and 12kB in size. We store the database file either on an in-memory partition (SQLite-tmpfs) or on a persistent drive, mounted using virtiofs in the SEV-Unikernel and Gramine cases. The VM was allocated a single core and 16GiB of memory. We report the results of read and write benchmarks in Figure 11.

When the database is stored on disk, however, Linux has a clear advantage over SEV-Unikernel and Gramine. We suppose this is largely due to inefficiencies in virtiofs. We test

Figure 12: NumPy performance

this hypothesis by testing Linux again with a virtiofs drive. We observed a runtime of 2.5-3.4X for read operations and 3.2-5.2X for write operations relative to Linux with a FAT32 partition. This shows that SEV-Unikernel performance is comparable to Linux, but that its lack of support for direct file system access makes it less ideal in operations that heavily rely on accessing the disk. The average AMD SEV impact on SEV-Unikernel is 4.7% for the in memory database and 34% on virtio. Gramine experiences similar overheads on TDX (6.2%/30.6%), whereas Linux has a low penalty in both cases (1.3%/2.4%).

7.5 NumPy

We select Python with NumPy support to demonstrate the ability to run interpreted languages in SEV-Unikernel. It is common for Python libraries to include functionalities written in C that are dynamically loaded during runtime. Since SEV-Unikernel does not support dynamic library loading, we had to statically compile these dependencies into the interpreter binary. To ensure comparability, the dependencies are compiled into the interpreter for all three systems. The Python standard library, as well as the benchmarking code, were supplied to the system in a virtiofs mount, except for Linux on AMD SEV and TDX where they were provided in a FAT32 partition. We measured the performance within Python using a number of benchmarks from the official NumPy repository.⁴

Figure 12 reveals very similar performances for all systems, with Gramine and Linux performing slightly better on average than SEV-Unikernel. The outliers of *LinalgSmallArrays* and *Polynomial* require further investigation.

7.6 TCB Size

As part of our evaluation, we analyze the size of the TCB for VMs running SEV-Unikernel, Gramine-VM, or Linux.

For Linux, we use the size of a minimal UEFI-compatible Ubuntu Linux 24.04 LTS cloud-image as the base size of the TCB, and obtain a size of 241MB. We argue this choice depicts a realistic deployment scenario of an application utilizing Linux in a TEE. While it is possible to further reduce the size of such an image, we claim that most users will not invest the time and effort of minimizing the image size as possible, and this effort would likely spare multiple

user-land programs such as the init daemon. However, we acknowledge that this assumption is debatable, and our goal in providing this estimation for Linux is to illustrate the order of magnitude and not to present precise numbers.

Both Linux and SEV-Unikernel both require an AMD SEV compatible OVMF firmware image to boot, which weighs 4.19M. We include this size in the base TCB size for both these operating systems.

SEV-Unikernel does not require any additional shared libraries as all necessary objects are linked statically to the kernel. In addition to the OVMF firmware, we must still take into account the boot-loader binary (114KB), and is included in the base TCB size of SEV-Unikernel.

For Gramine, the kernel and libOS contribute 1.25MB to the TCB size, which is in line with the number reported in [32]. Gramine also includes its own version of the GNU C library adding 2.2MB to its base TCB. In addition, Gramine includes shared libraries from the host system, which we consider on a per-application base and report in the ‘Shared Libs.’ column.

All application binaries have been stripped of unnecessary data with the `strip` tool. In the case of Unixbench, the benchmark is composed of multiple programs, so we report the averaged TCB size across all of them. As the NumPy and `lighttpd` benchmarks include additional files from the host, we include them in our TCB computations.

We report the resulting TCB sizes in Table 1. We see that the TCB size for SEV-Unikernel is relatively consistent, and roughly 30%-40% of this is contributed by the OVMF. Gramine, on the other hand, is able to forgo that 4MB increase of the OVMF thanks to the use of `td-shim`. Future work on similar light firmware solutions for AMD SEV would enable similar gains in SEV-Unikernel, with likely only minor modifications to the kernel code. Since SEV-Unikernel is written in Rust, support for C applications is achieved by cross-compiling the application with Hermit’s `newlib`⁵ port, which introduces a size increase compared to native Rust applications like `Hyper`.

A deeper look into SEV-Unikernel binaries reveals that a huge part of the image size is due to unnecessary relocation data. Due to a toolchain issue we did not fully investigate

⁴<https://github.com/numpy/numpy/tree/v2.3.3/benchmarks>

⁵<https://github.com/hermit-os/newlib>

Application	Common Mounted Files	SEV-Unikernel (incl. loader + OVMF)		Linux* (incl. cloud image + OVMF)		Gramine (incl. kernel + glibc)		
		Binary	Total	Binary	Total	Binary	Shared Libs.	Total
Unixbench	-	5.90MB	10.2MB	15.2KB	245MB	15.2KB	1.19MB	4.66MB
lighttpd	10.3KB	6.71MB	11.0MB	659KB	246MB	659KB	435KB	4.55MB
NumPy	5.20MB	25.2MB	34.7MB	19.9MB	270MB	19.9MB	4.08MB	27.3MB
Valkey	-	8.81MB	13.1MB	3.25MB	248MB	3.25MB	1.19MB	7.89MB
SQLite	-	6.71MB	11.0MB	713KB	246MB	713KB	236KB	4.4MB
Boot time	-	5.98MB	10.3MB	15.4KB	245MB	15.4KB	236KB	3.7MB
Hyper	-	5.35MB	9.65MB	1.89MB	247MB	1.89MB	1.37MB	6.71MB

Table 1: TCB sizes for SEV-Unikernel, Ubuntu Linux, and Gramine

due to time constraints, we were also not able to perform a full link-time optimization pass on our benchmarks for SEV-Unikernel, and therefore omitted it in all examples. Both optimizations are likely to bring a significant reduction in the binary size.

7.7 Discussion

As demonstrated by our experimental evaluation, SEV-Unikernel performs similar to Gramine-VM and Gramine-TDX. Instead, it performs significantly worse than Linux on network-bound benchmarks. The relative slowdown caused by the use of TEE technologies is comparable between all these platforms.

We believe that main reasons for the performance penalty lies in the task management of the Hermit kernel foundation. Indeed, the ability for a program to handle a lot of concurrent queries relies on the kernel processing network packets and executing program tasks quickly enough, which does not appear to be the case. We also found the performance of Hermit’s memory allocator suboptimal. SEV-Unikernel utilizes a different allocator, but we feel like there is further room for improvement.

The goal of this work was to provide a minimal TCB size for confidential applications and SEV-Unikernel achieves a notable reduction compared to Linux. The TCB size is also close to Gramine-TDX, whilst not reaching their level. However, Gramine-TDX is not available on AMD SEV, and is therefore not yet suitable for TCB reduction on that platform. As explained in §7.6, there are multiple plausible ways to improve this size further, which we leave for future work. This includes the development of an equivalent to `td-shim` as a replacement for OVMF, which contributes a significant portion of SEV-Unikernel’s TCB.

Gramine’s binary compatibility clearly minimizes the porting effort to the platform. Yet we found that the major burden of rebuilding for SEV-Unikernel lies in the often complex build systems for the applications, especially when these are tailored towards a shared library build. In the source code itself the most frequent burden is compile time switches only distinguishing between Linux and Windows specific code blocks.

Another advantage of the self contained approach of SEV-Unikernel lies in its robustness for deployment. There is no need for the host to provide the correct dependency versions, making it more suitable for cloud deployments.

8 Conclusion & Future Work

We have presented a novel approach to reduce the TCB size in AMD SEV CVMs based on unikernels, and have demonstrated the practicality of this approach through an implementation on AMD SEV, SEV-Unikernel. Our solution is also attestable, providing a closed chain-of-trust for confidential workloads. In our evaluation, we have shown that this approach achieves a significant TCB reduction at an acceptable performance cost of 1-34% compared to non-confidential VMs and often reaches similar performance as the Gramine-TDX unikernel. With regards to network performance, we still have a notable gap of 30% to 1150%. We believe that this gap is due not to conceptual issues but rather implementation issues originating in the base Hermit kernel, left for future work.

Our approach is not exclusive to the AMD SEV TEE, and an Intel TDX or ARM CCA variant of SEV-Unikernel could also be developed in future work, exploiting the base Hermit project and its native support for both x86_64 and ARM architectures. In addition, we have highlighted few limitations in the design of the Hermit kernel, including its scheduler and network stack, which need to be addressed to bridge the performance gap with Linux. Finally, achieving a maximal TCB reduction would require the development of a light OVMF replacement for AMD SEV virtual machines.

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